

Molybdenum : Part-VII. Dioxo Molybdenum (VI) Complexes with Benzoyl Phenyl Hydroxylamine or Substituted Hydroxylamine

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Reaction of $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ and benzoylphenyl hydroxylamine (or substituted hydroxylamines) in ethanol leads to the syntheses of bis N-Benzoylphenyl hydroxylamine-dioxo-molybdenum (VI) and related chelates. These are cream coloured, diamagnetic and their solution spectra reveal no ligand field bands in the visible region.

This study arose out of our programme of attempting syntheses of oxo-molybdenum(V) chelates of the well-known organic analytical reagent, N-Benzoylphenylhydroxylamine¹. Since the ligand has genuine reducing group, we thought reasonably that oxo-molybdenum (V) may be stabilised. Instead, we observed that the initial brown colour developed on the addition of MoOCl_3 to an alcoholic solution of the ligand rapidly changed to orange

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yellow and beautiful, cream-coloured needles of dioxo-molybdenum (VI) bis N-Benzoylphenylhydroxy-lamine were obtained. In this reaction, however traces of air could not be excluded from our reaction system. Evidently oxidation of Mo (V) to Mo (VI) was very fast. Two other substituted derivatives, namely N-Benzoyl *o*-tolyl-hydroxylamine and the corresponding *p*-tolyl derivative also provide similar, cream coloured complexes.

These complexes are diamagnetic and their solution spectra reveal no ligand field bands in the visible region.

We are therefore, justified in formulating these complexes as derivatives of molybdenum (VI). In keeping with the presence of a dioxo molybdenum (VI) group, the molybdenyl group absorbs much lower down around 940-945 cm^{-1} in the infrared² (Table II).

TABLE I

Analytical results and Molar extinction coefficient of the complexes (in chloroform)

Compound	% Mo	% N	Decomposition temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Wave length ($\text{m}\mu$)	ϵ
$\text{MoO}_2(\text{BPHA})_2$	F : 17.7	5.3	188-90	350	2250
	R : 17.39	5.07		410	114
$\text{MoO}_2(o\text{-tolyl})_2$	F : 17.0	4.7	185-86	350	2250
	R : 16.55	4.8		410	95
$\text{MoO}_2(p\text{-tolyl})_2$	F : 17.1	5.0	168-69	350	2250
	R : 16.55	4.8		410	145

BPHA = N-Benzoyl phenyl hydroxylamine ; *o*-tolyl = N-Benzoyl-*o*-tolyl hydroxylamine and *p*-tolyl = N-Benzoyl *p*-tolyl hydroxylamine.

Beyond 450 $\text{m}\mu$, the complexes did not absorb.

The insolubility of these complexes in methanol and ethanol has made difficult measurements of their conductances.

A search of literature indicates that the N-Benzoyl-N phenyl hydroxylamine compound has already been utilised for gravimetric estimation of molybdenum². A solvent extraction study has also indicated the same formula we have adduced to the complex³. However, our method of preparation has not been studied earlier and it is to be seen to what extent this technique is general in the syntheses of dioxo-molybdenum (VI) complexes.

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TABLE II
Infrared spectra of the complexes

Compound	Colour	stretching frequency (cm^{-1}) $\nu(0=\text{Mo}=0)$
$[\text{MoO}_2(\text{BPHA})_2]$	golden yellow	943
$[\text{MoO}_2(o\text{-tolyl})_2]$	,,	945
$[\text{MoO}_2(p\text{-tolyl})_2]$	,,	945

EXPERIMENTAL

The following substituted hydroxylamines were used to prepare compounds of Mo(VI) :

(a) N-Benzoyl, phenyl hydroxylamine was prepared by condensing freshly prepared phenyl hydroxylamine and benzoylchloride⁴, (b) N-Benzoyl *o*-tolyl hydroxylamine and (c) N-Benzoyl *p*-tolyl hydroxylamines were prepared according to Majumder *et al*⁵

Bis (N-Benzoyl phenyl/tolyl hydroxylamine)-dioxo molybdenum (VI) (Golden yellow). The reagent (3 moles), dissolved in minimum volume of rectified spirit, was mixed with a filtered solution of ammonium oxo-pentachloromolybdate (1 mole), dissolved in minimum volume of rectified spirit. Immediately a brown solution developed which quickly changed to orange yellow. The solution was refluxed on a sand bath for more than 30 minutes when cream coloured shining crystals separated. These are cooled, filtered, washed several times with spirit and dried over CaCl_2 .

The analytical results are given in Table I.

Analytical methods—Molybdenum content was estimated by decomposing the complex with equal volumes of concentrated H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 and then after adjusting the pH precipitating molybdenum with oxine and finally weighing as $\text{MoO}_2(\text{oxine})_2$.

Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro combustion technique.

Magnetic measurements—The magnetic susceptibility was determined by the Gouy method using a semimicro Mettler Balance for measuring the difference in weight with a field strength of 8.57×10^3 gauss.

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